

Enthalpies and Free Energies of Solvation of Sodium and Potassium Chlorides in Dimethyl Sulphoxide at 25°

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The solubilities of NaCl and KCl have been measured in DMSO in the temp. range 25°-95°. The solubilities increase slightly with temp. The enthalpies and free energies of solution and solvation have been calculated. Enthalpies and free energies of solvation of the electrolytes are plotted against $\frac{1}{r_+ + \delta}$. The individual ionic contributions obtained from the graph agree closely with those calculated from the modified Born equation. The adjustable parameter $\delta = 0.845 \text{ \AA}$ for cations and $0.39 \text{ \AA}$ for anions.

EVEN though much work has been done on the solvation of alkali halides in non-aqueous solvents like Formamide, NMF, DMF, CH_3CN , etc.^{1,2} little work seems to have been done on the solvation of sodium and potassium chlorides in DMSO. As the salts are not easily soluble, calorimetric measurements of the enthalpies of solvation are difficult and hence not attempted. The only other alternative is to get these from solubility data. Strangely enough only very little information is available on the solubility of these salts in DMSO and the data are not in agreement.^{3,4} An attempt is made in the present work to check the solubilities reported and to arrive at the enthalpies and free energies of solvation from solubility measurements.

Experimental

DMSO (B.D.H.) was purified by vac. fractionation.⁵ The middle fraction was repeatedly fractionated. The water content of the final product was estimated by Karl Fischer titration. It was found to be 0.001%. The physical constants at 25° were: m.p., 18.55°; d., 1.095 g cm⁻³; Sp. cond., 2.3×10^{-8} mho cm⁻¹.

Sodium and potassium chlorides (Merck.G.R.) were recrystallised twice from conductivity water and dried at 110° in vac. for several hours. The purity of the salts was determined gravimetrically; the purity was found to be NaCl 99.97 ± 0.01% and KCl 99.98 ± 0.01%.

Saturated solutions were prepared by the method given by A. J. Parker⁶. Solvent and the solutions were handled in a dry box. As DMSO is highly hygroscopic all precautions were taken to exclude moisture at every stage. Temperature was maintained in a thermostat within ± 0.01°. Weighed quantities of the solutions were analysed gravimetrically

both for the metal and for the chloride. Solubilities were calculated in g. per 100 g. of the solvent and as moles per Kg. of the solvent.

Results and Discussion

The solubilities of both the salts increase linearly with temperature. At all temperatures the solubility of KCl is less than that of NaCl. Solubilities of the salts at different temperatures are given in Table 1. The solubilities at 25° obtained in the present work agree well with those reported by C.A. Melendres⁴, but differ from those of Kenttamaa³.

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITIES OF NaCl AND KCl IN DMSO AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (g/100 G. OF THE SOLVENT)

Salts	25°	40°	50°	60°	70°	80°	94°
NaCl	0.455	0.465	0.472	0.478	0.485	0.491	0.501
KCl	0.168	0.174	0.178	0.183	0.187	0.191	0.197

$H_{(sat)}^\circ$ at 25° were calculated from the slope of $\log S$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$ graph. The plots are linear for both the salts in the temperature range studied showing that $\Delta H_{(sat)}^\circ$ is practically constant. The values are +0.30 and +0.511 K.cal. mole⁻¹ for NaCl and KCl respectively. Though these values of $\Delta H_{(sat)}^\circ$ may be different from the usual calorimetric ΔH° values, it is assumed that there will not be much change in these values due to heat of dilution since ion pair formation is reported to be negligible in DMSO⁷. Therefore values of enthalpies of solvation based on these $\Delta H_{(sat)}^\circ$ values may be only slightly in error.

The enthalpies of solvation of the salts are calculated from $\Delta H_{(sat)}^\circ$ and the lattice energies⁸ of these salts. According to the modified Born equation a plot of these enthalpies against $\frac{1}{r_+ + \delta}$ (r_+ is

the crystallographic radii of the cations and δ the adjustable parameter) should be a straight line for a closely related series of salts with a common anion.

The enthalpies of solvation of the salts $\text{LiCl}^{\ominus}$, NaCl and KCl are plotted against $\frac{1}{r_+ + \delta}$ of positive ions. A value of $\delta = 0.845 \text{ \AA}$ gave the best fitting straight line. The intercept of this line gives the enthalpy of solvation of the common anion—chloride (Fig. 1). The enthalpies of solvation of K^+ and Na^+ were calculated using this value. The enthalpy contribution of K^+ was also determined independently from a plot of the enthalpies of

solvation of KCl , KBr and KI vs $\frac{1}{r_- + \delta}$ of the anions ($\delta = 0.39 \text{ \AA}$)

The ionic enthalpies of solvation in DMSO were also calculated using the enthalpies of solvation of these ions in water and the enthalpies of transfer from water to DMSO reported by Arnett and McKelvey¹⁰. The agreement is found to be good.

The free energies of solvation are calculated from the solubility data.

$-\Delta G^\circ = 2 \times 2.303 RT \log (m \gamma_{\pm})$ where m is the solubility in moles Kg^{-1} and $\gamma_{\pm}$ the mean molal activity coefficient of the electrolyte in the saturated solution. $\gamma_{\pm}$ of NaCl is obtained by the authors from freezing point depression measurements. In the case of KCl $\gamma_{\pm}$ is calculated from Debye-Hückel limiting law. From the free energies of solution, the standard free energies of formation in the solvent and the free energies of solvation of the electrolytes are calculated by the method given by Criss and Luksha¹¹.

The free energies of solvation of the individual ions were determined graphically as in the case of enthalpies of solvation. These agree with those calculated from the modified Born equation,

The enthalpies and free energies of solvation of the salts are given in Table 2 and those of the ions in Table 3.

The free energies and enthalpies of solvation of the cations are more negative in DMSO than in water. This indicates that DMSO is a better solvating medium for the alkali ions. The enthalpies and free energies of solvation increase in the order $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$. On the other hand, the enthalpies and free energies of solvation of Cl^- are more positive than in water showing that the ion is less solvated. In DMSO, the centre of anion solvation is the S atom of the S-O dipole. This is sterically shielded by

TABLE 2—ENTHALPIES AND FREE ENERGIES OF SOLVATION OF LiCl , NaCl & KCl at 25° (K. cal. mole⁻¹)

Salt	ΔH° (sat)	Lattice energy	ΔH° (solv)	ΔG° (solv)	ΔG° (solv)	ΔG° (calc)
LiCl	-10.9 ± 3	-903.4	-214.3 ± 3	—	—	—
NaCl	+ 0.303	-185.8	-185.5	+ 3.58	-164.4	-164.48
KCl	+ 0.511	-168.0	-168.4	+ 4.93	-146.7	-148.65

TABLE 3—ENTHALPIES AND FREE ENERGIES OF SOLVATION OF Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^- at 25° (K. cal. mole⁻¹)

Ion	Radius $\text{\AA}$ (Pauling)	ΔH° (solv)	ΔH° (solv) (calc. from enthalpies of transfer)	ΔG° (solv)	ΔG° (solv) (Calc)
Li^+	0.60	-130.8	—	—	—
Na^+	0.95	-102.0	-101.75	-90.4	-90.57
K^+	1.33	-85.0	-84.64	-72.7	-74.74
Cl^-	1.81	-83.5	-83.87	-74.0	-73.91

the two methyl groups. Moreover charge density (+) of the S atom is decreased by the inductive effect of the two methyl groups. These combined effects seem to reduce the anion solvation. If anion solvation is the decisive factor in determining the relative solubilities in protic and dipolar aprotic solvents the lower solubilities of these salts in DMSO may be well explained by the low anion solvation existing in this solvent.

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